

Mathematics in vocational education: An epistemic framework

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In this methodological paper, we present a framework, which was developed in an action research project where mathematics teachers and vocational teachers collaborated with a researcher. With this epistemic framework we challenge the view where mathematics is taken-for-granted as the theoretical knowing which is applied to the practical vocational knowing. The purpose of the framework is to aid teachers and researchers to capture theoretical and practical aspects of mathematical and vocational knowing, both when the subject areas are separate, and when they are intertwined, in collaborative teaching. This way, power relations between different teaching contents may be reconstructed, which is helpful for collaborative teaching, and for students' learning in both mathematics and vocational teaching content areas.

Ways of investigating mathematics in relation to vocational contexts

In the literature, mathematics in relation to vocational contexts in educational settings is conceptualised in various ways. We will describe examples of these here in the introduction, and then we will put the emphasis on presenting and elaborating on an epistemic framework addressing theoretical and practical aspects of mathematical *and* vocational knowing. The framework has been presented elsewhere with a focus on general design theoretical aspects (Boistrup & Hällback, in press), and here we focus mainly on epistemic aspects of mathematics in relation to vocational knowing. We discuss the framework in relation to how mathematics can be made relevant to students who, as a group, often experience obstacles in learning mathematics within vocational education.

One perspective adopted in the literature is Bernstein's theory of pedagogic practice (2000), which has informed research on, for example, how mathematics is recontextualised in different workplace activities. One example is FitzSimons (2015), who adopted the concept of recontextualisation by Bernstein when investigating the vocational mathematics taking place within the workers' own industry workplace. In this project, workers could identify unsuspected ways of the mathematics they already knew being transformed into authentic workplace activities, while at the same time appreciating their own roles within the overall setting of the workplace. Another theoretical perspective adopted in the literature is activity system theory by Engeström (e.g., 2001). A recent example is Frejd and Muhrman (2020) who

Please cite as: Boistrup, L. B., & Hällback, M. (2021). Mathematics in vocational education: An epistemic framework. In D. Kollosche (Ed.), *Exploring new ways to connect: Proceedings of the Eleventh International Mathematics Education and Society Conference* (Vol. 1, pp. 311–320). Tredition. <https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.5393498>

investigated the learning space available for vocational mathematics education when carried out by teams with one mathematics teacher and one vocational teacher teaching collaboratively, as in this paper. The authors adopted the Engeström model in order to investigate notions like tools, norms, the division of labour and the community.

In critical mathematics education research with an interest in the characteristics of mathematical content in teaching, Chevallard's (e.g., 2006) Anthropological Theory of the Didactic (ATD), including the concept of praxeology, is quite often adopted (see, e.g., Straehler-Pohl & Gellert, 2013). Praxeology addresses two, albeit connected, dimensions of mathematical knowledge where praxis is *know-how* and logos is *know-why* (described below). Even though this model is mainly adopted in the literature of mathematics education, it is possible to adopt ATD also in other disciplines. This is described by Ladage, Achiam, and Marandino (2019), where one example is the didactic work in a museum. Another example is Quéré (2017), who investigated "mathematics in the workplace" in the context of engineering work in France. One outcome was that mathematics should not only be considered as a "tool" because engineers sometimes need to have an accurate understanding of the actual tools they use. Castela (2015) discussed the opportunities of adopting ATD in research on mathematics in connection to other knowledge areas, such as dress-making. The following quote highlights our rationale for choosing ATD as the framework we present:

This anthropology of the mathematics should investigate social practices without too narrow restrictions on what is an interesting object. That is why I consider the praxeological model as previously presented as an interesting tool. It highlights dimensions of the institutional cognition that would be neglected otherwise, especially when the reference to acknowledged mathematics is too strong. (p. 18)

Background of the project

Boistrup, Bellander, and Blaesild (2018), in a study by the first author of this paper together with two teachers, drew on Bernstein's concept of recontextualisation to identify how mathematics was relocated and transformed (i.e., recontextualised) in vocational education (construction work). One conclusion, roughly speaking, was that there are at least two distinct ways to recontextualise mathematics in vocational activities. One is the explicit use of mathematics in, for example, problem solving, and another is mathematical concepts and methods being integrated –more implicitly – into the vocational activity. This project was helpful in finding ways to describe the interfaces between two teaching content areas, mathematics and construction work. Not surprisingly, in a survey with open questions, the students described that they found mathematics more accessible when the mathematics teacher and the construction work teacher taught together and discussed the different content areas' relationships. Since mathematics is the teaching subject which causes most problems for students in the Swedish upper secondary school to pass, this was of course good news. A surprise to the teachers and researcher in the project was that the students also expressed that the involvement of mathematics helped them in learning the vocational content.

In a subsequent action research project, in which the authors of this paper took part, new steps were taken in order to go into more detail on how epistemic aspects could be understood and interpreted when mathematics is taught in connection to vocational teaching content. The reason was that when the mathematics teacher and the vocational teacher taught collaboratively for one class per week, they wanted to move beyond a focus on practical matters and on which tasks to bring into the teaching. Instead they aimed at making mathematics relevant for the students in relation to the vocational teaching content, and to focus on explanations and reasoning in both teaching content areas. The researcher's choice then was to turn to Chevallard (2006) and his model of praxeology, both because praxeology consists of concepts which articulate epistemic aspects (described below), and because it is possible to adopt praxeology for analysis in a broad range of disciplines, including vocational knowing.

Why this epistemic framework?

The purpose of the framework is to aid teachers and researchers to capture theoretical and practical aspects of mathematical and vocational knowing, both when the subject areas are separate, but also when they are intertwined, as in collaborative teaching. This way, the power relations between the different teaching content areas may be reconstructed, which is helpful for collaborative teaching, and for students' learning in both mathematics and vocational teaching content.

We challenge the dichotomous conception where mathematics is taken as the theoretical knowing as opposed to the vocational knowing which is taken as purely practical. Rather, we view theoretical work as being developed by means of a variety of resources (such as body movements, artefacts, speech, and the like), maintained and changing over time in human practices (Selander, 2006) such as vocations and mathematics, as in the case of this paper. Rosvall, Hjelmer, and Lappalainen (2017) point to a connected tension between workplace and so-called academic knowing in vocational education in Sweden and Finland. This tension, as Rosvall et al. write, is exacerbated through the idea of a vocational learner as being practically oriented; using their hands instead of their heads and positioned as being in need. Such ideas constitute institutional norms, affecting the setting in which the teaching is designed. Through the framework presented in this paper it is possible, in research and teaching, to move beyond such ideas, and to strive to actively identify theoretical and practical aspects of different teaching content areas (in the case of this paper, mathematics and hair & makeup styling).

In Sweden, a large part of vocational education is included as study programs within upper secondary school, alongside study programs aiming for university studies. In these programs, the curriculum covers both the knowledge specified for the vocation in question, including periods of practicum, and general knowledge areas, for example English and Mathematics. In some schools, the vocational teacher and the mathematics teacher teach one lesson together each week, at least with the 1st year students. At one such school, a mathematics teacher (Hällback) was given the responsibility to take the lead in a process of

developing collaborative teaching between mathematics and vocational teachers, affording possibilities of learning for the students. As part of this, Hällback made contact with a researcher, Boistrup, and a joint action research project was initiated with four teachers at the school and one researcher.

Figure 1: Student's face chart (left) and a student drawing triangles (right).

The framework of this paper was developed as part of the project and was helpful for the teachers in each team (one mathematics teacher and one vocational teacher). The examples in this paper derive from a lesson in the vocational knowledge area of styling, where the focus was on how to use triangles when doing facial makeup (see Figure 1). The lesson was video recorded, and documents and artefacts were photographed.

Theoretical underpinnings

In our action research project, we had a great interest in understanding vocational knowing aspects in relation to mathematics and, as mentioned above, we chose to draw on the model of praxeology. Praxeology is a model addressing the characteristics of knowing, and is part of Chevallard's (2006) ATD. Castela (2015) described ATD as being "interested in the processes and products of what we may consider as the institutional cognition, that is to say, in how institutions develop their socially acknowledged capitals of practices and knowing" (p. 8).

According to Chevallard (2006), praxeology is constituted by praxis and logos and offers us a foundation for addressing the practical and theoretical aspects in, and the connections between knowledge areas such as mathematics and vocational knowing. *Praxis* (know-how) concerns *tasks* (types of assignments) and *techniques* (procedures with which the task type can be carried out). An example of a vocational task in the project was curling hair with three different kinds of curls, while the mathematical task was to identify the angles of 45, 90, and 180 degrees, respectively, between the loop of hair and the surface of the skull. When curling the hair, aspects of the vocational technique concerned for example how to capture a loop of hair with the curling iron in a functional way. A mathematical technique could be to direct the loop of hair in the proper direction for the angle to be the intended one. *Logos*

(know-why) concerns *technologies* (why a procedure works in the way it does) and *theories* (overarching structures on a general level). An example of a technology connected mainly to styling was why the curling iron needs to be handled in a certain way in relation to how it affects the hair, while a mathematical technology was the explanation of why a direction of a hair loop creates a 90-degree angle and not 180 degrees. The main function of theory is then to provide a basis for the technology (Bosch & Gascón, 2014). This basis may be constituted by axioms, traditions, research findings, or theoretical assumptions. An example of a theory connected to the vocational knowing from the data was the overarching knowledge about hair styles, where curling all hair loops with the same angle creates for example a hair style similar to what Marilyn Monroe had. Examples of theoretical aspects more connected to mathematics were what constitutes the concept of an angle including the correct mathematical terminology.

We also drew on a theoretical perspective, based on social semiotics and institutional theory: Designs for Learning (DfL) (Selander, 2021). In DfL, the setting is always part of the analysis of teaching events, incorporating the resources available and the institutional norms which may restrict and/or provide opportunities for the teaching. Furthermore, in DfL the multimodal character of all communication is emphasized, with an interest in how knowing is transformed between and within modes (for example, speech, text, images, symbols) in all communication. These modes hold affordances for students' learning.

The framework

Through the project, we identified the praxis and logos of both vocational and mathematical knowing. The four Ts in the model – task, technique, technology, and theory – are intertwined and constituted by each other. Analytically, we identified them in the data from the collaborative teaching in styling and mathematics. For the analysis of knowing aspects, we developed a model (Figure 2), which reflects the epistemic framework.

	Styling			Mathematics		
Task						
Technique						
Technology						
Theory						

Figure 2: A framework for capturing a continuum of aspects of knowing within styling and mathematics, and the intertwinement of both.

The framework in Figure 2 provides the opportunity to identify epistemic aspects that are a mixture of styling and mathematics, as well as aspects “belonging” more to either of the two knowledge areas, while at the same time identifying the praxis (task and technique) and logos (technology and theory) aspects.

Examples from collaborative teaching

When it comes to the setting of the makeup lesson, the location was the styling teaching rooms with the consequence that the learning resources connected to styling were there, with mirrors, hair and makeup materials, et cetera. The mathematics teacher added learning resources to the teaching as well, as will be shown below. The curriculum in the sense of teaching content derived from both styling and mathematics, with knowing aspects concerning carrying out makeup through highlighting and contouring, and handling triangles from a mathematical perspective. The institutional norm, that there is value in drawing on vocational knowing in the teaching of mathematics, is very much present. The overarching assignment of the lesson was a combination of these knowledge areas: to carry out facial makeup through the use of triangles. This overarching assignment consisted of task types, for example to know which parts of the face to highlight, and which parts to make darker through contouring. In order to make the modes and resources clear, the video episode is transcribed multimodally, with columns addressing various modes (see Excerpt 1).

In the first example, the styling teacher (D) discusses how the students should proceed to place triangles on the face (see Figure 1b). Normally, a stylist does not draw triangles on a person’s face with clear lines, but during this lesson students would do this to emphasize the moment of seeing triangles in the face while doing makeup. Seeing the triangles facilitates, among other things, the work of making a face more symmetrical through make-up (which is a theoretical aspect, not highlighted by the teacher during this event). Before this event, D has asked some students where they can find relevant triangles on the face:

Time	Speech	Body movements and resources
20:07	D: You are <u>really good</u> ; you know exactly where on the face the triangles should be.	Dips his makeup brush on the back of the hand, stands slightly forward leaning
20:08		Carries out make-up on a student under the eyebrows with light strokes
	[...]	
20:16	D: Here, here we should have light, right? And then we take all that	D puts a lot of makeup on the student's jawbone and tries to show a clear triangle

Excerpt 1. The styling teacher (D=Divo) discusses positions of triangles with a student (S).

The focus in Excerpt 2 is on the actual *technique* of doing makeup with the support of triangles. D articulates this in words (“...you know exactly where on the face the triangles

should be”) in coordination with body movements and resources. The word “triangle” communicated through speech is transformed by D into body movements when he shows triangles as part of carrying out the technique of makeup. This transformation is part of making the technique clear to the students. This event received the following position in the framework (Figure 3):

	Styling		Mathematics		
Task					
Technique					
Technology					
Theory					

Figure 3. The interactions in Excerpt 1 interpreted as a technique with the focus equally on styling and mathematics.

The placement in the middle column in Figure 3 is due to the fact that D largely directs the students’ attention to the triangles of the face (part of mathematical knowing), at the same time as he does this from a styling perspective.

The next example is that the mathematics teacher (M) and a student are looking for triangles on a face chart, as a basis for the makeup to be done (Excerpt 2). As mentioned previously, *theory*, in praxeology by Chevallard (2006), is about overall knowing and ideas which form the basis as to why *technologies* can explain certain *techniques*. The example in Excerpt 2 was interpreted to display knowing reflecting different areas of the model in the framework.

Time	Speech	Body movements and resources
23:01	M: Exactly mm... and then you can imagine that you have a triangle kind of like this... or?	Is squatting beside S. S looks at M, who makes a triangle in the forehead with her fingers
23:04	M: Or you want it so that it...	Shows with her fingers in the opposite direction.
	[...]	
23:24	M: Hey look at you! You can really find many triangles.	Looks at the student.
	[...]	

23:32	M: Here we can make rather small triangles. Like <u>this</u> , right?	Shows with her thumb and index finger how thin the triangle may be.
23:34	M: Which has a small base.	Shows with both index fingers in the air, how small it may be.
23:26	M: But with higher sides, kind of.	Draws upwards with the index fingers. S nods.
23:29	M: So... there, right? Right under...	Points at the cheek of the face of the student's paper. S nods.

Excerpt 2: The mathematics teacher (M) and a student (S) are looking for triangles on a face chart, as a basis for the makeup to be done.

Excerpt 2 shows that M emphasizes that triangles can look very different from each other. The aspects of the interaction where they looked for triangles of the face, led to the middle box in the row of technology, since they were justifying how and why to use triangles when doing makeup. At the same time, they discussed the properties of the different triangles found, and this was inferred to concern theoretical aspects of mathematics:

	Styling		Mathematics		
Task					
Technique					
Technology					
Theory					

Figure 4. The interactions in Excerpt 2 interpreted as a technology with an equal focus on styling and mathematics, drawing on mathematical theory.

M also uses various terms that are relevant to descriptions of triangles, such as the word “base.” This belongs to the overall mathematical knowing, which justifies the placement in the box in the lower right corner of Figure 4.

Discussion

In this paper, we have illuminated how it is possible to carry out a detailed analysis of data from collaborative teaching, with attention to aspects concerning for example transformations between modes/resources, and practical and theoretical aspects of knowing. With the attention to how theoretical and practical aspects of knowing can be understood as part of practices, we have contributed with a framework which challenges a dichotomous understanding of mathematics in relation to vocational knowing. The framework of this paper can

be viewed as a didactic model possible to adopt for teachers and researchers with a specific interest, such as collaborative teaching in mathematics and for example vocational subjects.

From a design theoretical perspective, this paper illuminates the setting of the teaching in terms of the institutional norms of the school, where it was promoted that mathematics should be integrated with vocational teaching for one lesson a week. Another setting aspect concerns resources where the paper describes how the styling classroom had many authentic artefacts which helped to strengthen aspects of knowing in styling, and also in mathematics. This is similar to the findings by Frejd and Muhrman (2020), although the framework of this paper extends the multimodal focus of the analysis, which also deepens the understanding of the meaning making that was afforded through the teaching. One example in the form of an artefact was the face chart which is normally used in styling practices, but was now also used with a focus on mathematical aspects such as symmetry and triangles. This focus, in turn, helped the styling content to be articulated more clearly. Through our attention to how knowing aspects were transformed between modes, we also identified the extent to which the knowing aspects reflected mathematics and styling, and also whether they were mainly about praxis or logos.

This paper aimed to take both mathematics and vocational knowing seriously, and to not take for granted that mathematics in vocational activities is not simply materialised as school mathematics. The framework of this paper adds ways of capturing the character of mathematical and vocational knowing in an educational setting, and how these knowledge areas can relate to each other in many different ways, and through a variety of modes. We argue that such a framework is helpful in making mathematics relevant for students attending vocational education programs, not least since it was shown in the project that a deliberate epistemic focus created opportunities for teaching and learning in both mathematics *and* styling.

Acknowledgement

We would like to express our gratitude to reviewers, editors, and Gail FitzSimons for their help with the revision of this text.

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